

A PEDAGOGICAL MODEL FOR DEVELOPING BIOETHICAL CULTURE IN BIOLOGY STUDENTS BASED ON INTERDISCIPLINARY COOPERATION

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Abstract: The article studies the theoretical and methodological foundations of the development of bioethical culture in biology students, the pedagogical system of developing bioethical culture in biology students in interdisciplinary cooperation, the effectiveness of developing bioethical culture in biology students in interdisciplinary cooperation. Also, the theoretical aspects of developing bioethical culture in biology students are analyzed.

Key words: biology, technology, bioethical culture, improvement, pedagogical, technological, model, didactic, form, method, tool, evaluation, creative thinking, interdisciplinary cooperation, digital technologies.

Introduction.

Today, in the process of improving the system of biological education, particular emphasis is being placed on the primacy of ethical criteria and the integration of biological approaches with moral principles. This issue is becoming increasingly relevant, especially in the formation of bioethical knowledge and in enhancing moral responsibility. The development of bioethical culture among students in the field of biology is closely linked to disciplines such as medicine and philosophy, biology, religion, law, human rights movements, and social studies. It reflects the theoretical foundations of modern bioethical knowledge and addresses the major issues of practical medicine. In order to teach bioethics effectively in higher biological education, it is essential to study and understand both national and key international documents, to adopt a reasoned approach to real-life situations, to identify the moral problems arising in these contexts, and most importantly, to contribute to shaping the moral image of the new generation of healthcare professionals.

Literature review and methods.

The necessity of developing bioethics, the bioethical aspects of contemporary medicine, the consequences of biopower in the era of advanced biotechnologies, the role of biotechnologies in preserving human health, and the development of bioethical worldview, thinking, and culture have been studied by scholars such as Z. Mukhammedova, F. Zaghidinova, R. Khudoyberganov, N.

Umrzoqova, Sh. Isakhova, M. Nurmatova, Y. Vodopyanova, Y. Lopukhin, Y. Tishchenko, F. Nejmiddinova, A. Papova, M. Lanovskiy, and R. Belyaletdinov.

Results and discussion.

To develop bioethical culture among students of biology, foundational modules such as philosophy, ethics, law, religious studies, history, and biology provide the theoretical basis. In addition, they serve as a foundation for disciplines such as biochemistry, biophysics, biotechnology, bioecology, and bioethics.

In fostering the development of bioethical culture among biology students, it is crucial to:

- understand the unique characteristics of bioethics;
- cultivate the ability to effectively analyze and resolve ethical issues encountered in medicine and professional practice;
- instill awareness of general moral values such as the physician's duty, honor, dignity, integrity, and justice;
- master the clinical and humanitarian foundations of the profession;
- develop scientific and methodological competence.

The goals of teaching courses such as *"Biochemistry and Molecular Biology"*, *"Biophysics"*, *"Biotechnologies"*, and the elective *"Bioethics"* in an integrated manner for biology students include:

- introducing students to the historical theories of ethics and key issues in bioethics;
- forming bioethical principles in students, instilling biomedical ethical norms, and increasing sensitivity to moral issues;
- developing students' practical skills in analyzing biomedical ethics and moral problems;
- forming a comprehensive understanding of ethical values and the regulation and resolution of moral conflicts;
- familiarizing students with relevant scholarly literature.

Within the framework of the bioethical approach, the development of the following knowledge, skills, and competencies should be prioritized:

- understanding of basic ethical terms and concepts;
- awareness of major ethical theories;
- familiarity with methods used in bioethics;
- comprehension of the moral and ethical standards of professional medical ethics and models of bioethics.

ahloqiy muammolarni falsafiy tahlil qili usullaridan foydalanishni;

o'z amaliyotida tibbiy deontologiya va tibbiy etikaning ahloqiy normalari, qoidalari va tamoyillaridan foydalanish, shuningdek, kasbiy tibbiy hatti-harakatlarni to'g'ri amalga oshirishni;

fikrlar xilma-xilligi asosida munozaralar olib borish, nizolarni hal etishning turli ahloqiy usullaridan foydalanishni;

shifokorlar va turli yoshdagi bemorlarning fuqarolik huquqlarini himoya qilishni;

fuqarolik jamiyati hayotida faol ishtirok etish, insonparvarlik tamoyillari va umuminsoniy qadriyatlarga amal qilishni;

fikrlashning ilmiy uslub va tamoyillarini;

tibbiy deontologiya va tibbiy etika asoslarini;

bemorlar bilan ahloqiy munosabatlarni shakllantirishni bilishi va ulardan foydalana olishi;

ahloqiy madaniyat ko'nikmalari, bahs-munozaralarda mustaqil nuqtai nazarni taqdim etish;

tibbiy amaliyotda uchraydigan muammoli ahloqiy va huquqiy masalalarini hal qilish, bemorning manfaatlarini himoya qilish;

omma nutqini tahlil qilish va mantiqiy fikrlash malakalariga (shu jumladan ko'nikmalariga) ega bo'lishi kerak.

In organizing integrative education, just as the unity of integration and differentiation is considered a key principle, the unity of integration, differentiation, and humanitarization is also a fundamental principle in the humanization of education. It is known that from the perspective of philosophical viewpoints, integration and differentiation are interdependent and inseparable categories that define each other.

The process of the integration of knowledge has revealed another universal law related to the process of cognition. In other words, as scientific and technological progress advances and relevant knowledge deepens, it becomes evident that all disciplines—such as biology and physics, physics and chemistry—play a role, necessitating a comprehensive understanding of phenomena and processes. This, in turn, creates the opportunity to integrate knowledge obtained across various disciplines when studying a given process. Modern integration reflects another essential characteristic of the laws governing cognition: it aims to deepen and solidify knowledge about natural phenomena and processes.

The goal-oriented block plays a leading role in the system for developing the bioethical culture of biology students, serving as the foundation for the

content of other blocks in the system. On the basis of defining this block's content, the relevant educational standards, social demand, and normative-legal frameworks in the field of study were identified. In addition, the objectives and tasks of the model were clarified.

The development of biology students' bioethical culture was identified as a social demand through legal and regulatory documents such as the Law "On Education" and the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System in the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030.

In the process of developing the model, the following tasks were addressed: identifying the methodological approaches for the model development; defining the block structure of the model; uncovering the relationships among the model's blocks and elements; and characterizing the block structure and its elements.

The aforementioned goals and objectives of developing the bioethical culture of biology students are tied to complex methodological approaches.

The next block of the model reflects the aspect of performance outcomes. This block fulfills an evaluative function and represents the practical dimension of the research. It reflects the levels, criteria, and indicators of the development of bioethical culture among biology students.

A review of contemporary literature on the issue indicates that the main measurement criteria reflect a higher level of personal development.

The study identifies the following three evaluation criteria:

1. Cognitive;
2. Activity-based;
3. Axiological.

A tiered approach was used in the study to assess the level of development of biology students' bioethical culture. This approach enables the analysis of the dynamics of the studied process by examining transitions from one level to another based on each criterion. Determining the level of development and providing its justification was conducted through experimental work aimed at understanding the general direction of the problem and identifying students' initial level of preparedness. During the training process, students develop from a lower to an acceptable level.

The effectiveness of developing the bioethical culture of biology students is determined by the presence of certain qualitative changes. In the study, the following developmental levels of bioethical culture were identified:

- Basic (low),

- Good (medium),
- Satisfactory (high).

Conclusion

Based on the results of the research, it was concluded that in the process of developing the bioethical culture of biology students, a complex of pedagogical models aimed at applying practical skills, fostering student engagement, expanding social knowledge, and promoting social activity may serve as an effective means of ensuring success. In this regard, we can identify exemplary teaching models such as: students' assimilation of clearly defined patterns; students' educational and investigative activities based on the main types of bioethics; systematic cognitive inquiry by students into types of scientific research; and training in dialogic activity. It was revealed that in higher biological education, while the methodology of teaching specialized subjects has been studied, insufficient attention has been paid to the formation of bioethical knowledge. As a result, a methodology for developing bioethical culture based on interdisciplinary cooperation was developed.

References:

1. Makhmudov M. Designing Educational Outcomes. "Pedagogical Skills", 2003, No. 1, pp. 8–10.
2. Mukhamedova Z. M. The Problem of Brain Death in Islamic Bioethics // Humanitarian Treatise – 2017. – No. 17, pp. 15–19.
3. Pedagogy. General editorial supervision by M. Toktakhodjaeva. – Tashkent: "Philosophers' National Society of Uzbekistan", 2010.
4. Tishchenko P. D. The Phenomenon of Bioethics // Questions of Philosophy. – 1992. – No. 3, pp. 104–113.
5. Khodjaev B.Q., Juraev B.T. Introduction to Pedagogical Activity. Monograph. – Tashkent, 2019, pp. 124–128.

